

Semi-structured Interviews coding

Theme	Details	Example	N participants
Need for guidance	Expression of desire or appreciation for recommendations relative to their data	"Here's my result, should I do something about it?" "A device should do more than just log"	10/16
Motivation	Idea that motivation to perform better is the main reason behind the usage of self-tracking technologies	"It really motivates me to try and go further each time"	8/16
Data sharing aversion	Expression of dislike or disinterest towards sharing their own personal data on social medial or real life	"I never even tell people I track what I eat, let alone share it. I don't think anybody would care"	5/16
Privacy and toilet sharing	Mentions of issues of privacy or other's people sharing of the toilet	"They already know everything, I don't want to give something more" "I don't want my guests to see it and freak out!"	6/16
Effort and manipulation	Mentions of the personal effort that would be needed to use a tracking device, or the act of manipulating it and the toilet	"I used a calorie tracking app for two weeks, but it was too time consuming, complicated, and lacked joy" "I would like some level o f automation, unless it's just like a clearblue"	5/16
Usefulness	Comments regarding the urine tracking device being useful or interesting	"It could really change people's medical routine, especially if you have something like diabetes"	5/16
Loss of interest	Mentions of participants stopping using self-tracking technologies for loss of interest	"I use them a lot in the beginning, but I quickly lose curiosity"	3/16
Data sharing liking	Expression of appreciation towards sharing their own personal data on social media or real life	"Look at me, I'm good!"	1/16
Tracking of other people aversion	Doubts or dislike regarding using the urine tracking device for tracking of others (e.g. children, parents)	"I would never use it like that I think, it feels like crossing boundaries"	8/16
Data anxiety	Idea that having access to too much personal data can bring anxiety	"Sometimes having too much information makes patients anxious"	2/16
Dealing with urine	Mentions of not being bothered or disgusted about the idea of dealing with urine in the context of-tracking	"You have to clean the toilet anyways, so what does it change?"	8/16